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1. Purpose

- To uncover fatigue mechanisms in fibre composites
- To create micromechanical model for prediction of fatigue life from microscale parameters

3. Microscale fatigue damage mechanism

- Fibre failures occur in regions (damage zones)
- Clear demarcation between damage zones (where all fibres are broken) and surrounding material (no broken fibres)
- Location of new fibre failure is close to failure location of previously broken fibre
- About 10 more fibres fail within 10.000 cycles

Damage zone size

Damage zone size

2. Experimental methods

- Tensile test specimen subjected to cyclic loading (maximum 1.0% strain, R-ratio = 0.1)
- Instrumentation: extensometer and themovision
- Tests interrupted at 10.000 cycles interval for X-ray imaging
- 3D fatigue damage characterization by X-ray tomography

4. Conceptual model (fatigue mechanism)

- Fibre failure is accompanied by fibre/matrix debonding
- Debond length of broken fibre increases during cycling (decrease of interfacial friction)
- Debond crack tip stress field (K-field) approach a defect in a neighbouring fibre and induces failure in the neighbouring fibre

References

- Jespersen, K. M., and Mikkelsen, L. P. 2017, "Three dimensional fatigue damage evolution in non-crimp glass fibre fabric based composites used for wind turbine blades", Composites Science and Technology. Vol. 153, pp. 261-272.
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